

Data Management Plan

NYC real estate linear regression

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Based on: *Common DSW Knowledge Model, 2.0.1 (dsw:root:2.0.1)*

Generated on: 27 Apr 2020

Data Management Plan created in Data Stewardship Wizard <<https://ds-wizard.org>>

Abstract

For this experiment, I've decided to choose NYC Property Sales dataset from (<https://www.kaggle.com/new-york-city/nyc-property-sales>). This dataset holds information on properties sold in New York City over a 12-month period from September 2016 to September 2017. I've created the experiment of price prediction model for purposes of this project.

In the next chapters, dataset will be described in more detail and all relevant columns will be visualized to understand their relationships and effect on the model.

Section A: Data Collection

1. What data will you collect or create?

Instrument datasets

The following instrument datasets will be acquired in the project:

- **nyc-rolling-sales.csv**

This dataset will be collected by experts in the project, with our own equipment.

The equipment is very well described and known.

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- [CSV Dialect Description Format](#)

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

2. How will the data be collected or created?

Instrument datasets

- **nyc-rolling-sales.csv**

For this dataset, we are using the following instruments:

- **Python** – Python is an interpreted, high-level, general-purpose programming language
- **Jupyter Notebook** – The Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web application that allows you to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualizations and explanatory text

We will not be using quality process for this dataset.

Storage and file conventions

We will use a filesystem with files and folders with the following folder conventions:

- There will be a **folder for each sample/subject**. Each of those will use the following conventions: dataset , images, src.

We will not be storing data in an "object store" system.

We will not use a relational database system to store project data.

We will not use a graph database for data in the project.

We will not be storing data in a triple store.

Section B: Documentation and Meta-data

3. What documentation and meta-data will accompany the data?

List of data to be published is given in Section E, Question 9. This also includes information about catalogs where the data can be found. Information about data types used is given in Section A, Question 1.

Section C: Ethics and Legal Compliance

4. How will you manage any ethical issues?

5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All of our data can become completely open immediately.

Section D: Storage and Backup

6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data that project members themselves store adequately backed up and traceable. Therefore data are protected against both equipment failure and human error.

7. How will you manage access and security?

Project members will not store data or software on computers in the lab or external hard drives connected to those computers. They will not carry data with them (e.g. on laptops, USB sticks, or other external media). All data centers where project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All project web services addressed via secure http (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The possible impact to the project or organization if information is lost is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is small. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small.

We are not using any personal information.

Section E: Selection and Preservation

8. Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

We plan to publish the following datasets:

- **nyc-rolling-sales** – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible.

9. What is the longterm preservation plan for the dataset?

- **nyc-rolling-sales** will be stored in a domain-specific repository: [GitHub](#). We don't need to contact the repository because it is a routine for us. We will be adding a reference to the published data to at least one data catalogue.

None of the used repositories charge for their services.

Section F: Data Sharing

10. How will you share the data?

- **nyc-rolling-sales** – freely available for any use (public domain or CC0).

Information about used repositories (i.e. where will potential users find out about the data) is provided in Section E, Question 9.

Embargo on the data is described in Section C, Question 5, and Section F, Question 11.

11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Ethical and legal restrictions are documented under Section C. We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard, which made us aware of options to minimize the restrictions.

No data sharing agreement will be required.

Section G: Responsibilities and Resources

12. Who will be responsible for data management?

Tomas Drietomsky is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

Charges applied by data repositories (if any) are mentioned already in Section E, Question 9.